

Context-Aware IoT Smart Hub: A Semantic and Cognitive Architecture for Adaptive Internet of Robotic Things Environments.

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Abstract—This paper presents the IoT Smart Hub, a local, modular infrastructure designed to enhance adaptive interoperability, semantic context perception, and action validation in Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT) ecosystems. A new M2M2PA (Machine-to-Machine-to-Perception-and- Actuation) paradigm is also proposed, integrating semantic reasoning and real-time feedback into the communication cycle. Preliminary results demonstrate its capacity to structure contextual data and support cognitive agents, such as Large Language Models (LLMs), for natural language interaction and future reinforcement learning integration.

Index Terms—IoRT; Smart Hub; M2M2PA; Semantic Context; Cognitive Agents.

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution from the Internet of Things (IoT) to the Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT) has intensified the complexity of cyber-physical ecosystems, marked by heterogeneous devices, autonomous agents, and dynamic contexts (1), (2). These environments demand interoperability, real-time synchronization, semantic perception, and adaptive behavior, requirements that exceed the capabilities of traditional M2M architectures (3), (4).

Despite efforts using frameworks like Home Assistant, local interoperability remains limited due to protocol heterogeneity and lack of contextual cohesion (6; 11). Even recent middleware based on NGSI-LD and microservices fail to support semantic integration, action validation, and context-driven autonomy (5), (6), (7), (8).

To address these gaps, we propose the IoT Smart Hub: a modular infrastructure based on the M2M2PA (Machine-to-Machine-to-Perception-and-Actuation) paradigm. It integrates semantic context modeling and feedback validation, offering structured data to support cognitive agents, as BDI and LLMs in IoRT environments.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. IoRT, Multi-Agent Systems, and Cognitive Integration

The Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT) extends IoT by integrating autonomous agents and robotic systems for distributed, context-aware operation (1), (2). This raises challenges in semantic heterogeneity, synchronization, and adaptive control. Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) offer a natural coordination model in such settings (9).

To address these demands, *cognitive agents*, capable of learning and reasoning, are gaining relevance in domains like smart homes and robotics. Casals et al. (8) define *Augmented Agents* as extensions of classical models with integrated perception, planning, and learning. The Belief–Desire–Intention (BDI) framework remains a core architecture, relying on structured, context-rich data often missing in current IoT infrastructures.

B. Communication Architectures for IoT Interoperability

Recent proposals have tackled semantic interoperability in IoT. FIWARE (NGSI-LD) enables context modeling but lacks action feedback and adaptive learning (5). IoT-InterArch adds semantic abstraction but falls short in dynamic responsiveness (6), while IoT Redirector improves routing but not high-level reasoning (7).

Other relevant solutions include: Home Assistant (modular but lacks semantics) (11), EdgeX Foundry (protocol-rich, but semantically limited) (12), and oneM2M (standardized, but rigid) (13). More recent tools like Semantic Node-RED (14), SIM (15), TSMATCH (16), and Ranpara’s Ontology-Based Framework (17) enhance semantic layers but still lack action validation and integration with cognitive agents. Gill et al. highlight recurring issues: low semantic depth, poor contextual adaptability, and absence of feedback loops (3).

These gaps underline the demand for a local, modular, and semantically enhanced infrastructure, capable of bridging device-level interoperability with cognitive agent requirements. The following section presents the proposed IoT Smart Hub, built upon the novel M2M2PA paradigm, as a response to these architectural and reasoning demands.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION: IOT SMART HUB WITH M2M2PA APPROACH

As Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT) ecosystems grow increasingly complex, combining heterogeneous devices, autonomous agents, and dynamic environments. Therefore, there is a critical need for architectures that surpass conventional connectivity and rule-based automation. We propose the IoT Smart Hub: a modular, semantic infrastructure designed to support adaptive interoperability, contextual perception, and seamless integration with cognitive agents. The Hub serves as a local bridge between low-level IoT components and high-level decision-making in distributed systems.

A. Overview of the Modular Architecture

The IoT Smart Hub consists of three core modules, as highlighted on Fig. 1:

- **Smart Context Manager:** Orchestrates sensor/actuator interaction and middleware communication by:
 - Capturing environmental data;
 - Executing and validating actions;
 - Annotating events semantically.
- **Semantic Local Store (Contextual BD):** A database organized via semantic triples and lightweight ontologies that:
 - Records states, actions, and outcomes;
 - Enables retrospective reasoning and contextual inference.
- **Integration Layer (Home Assistant + MQTT):**
 - Interfaces with heterogeneous devices (e.g., ZigBee, BLE);
 - Facilitates asynchronous, modular communication.

B. Objectives and Operational Goals

Key goals of the IoT Smart Hub include:

- Facilitating adaptive communication between devices and agents;
- Structuring local semantic context for reasoning;
- Executing actions with feedback loops;
- Enabling cognitive integration (e.g., LLMs, RL).

C. M2M2PA Paradigm: Enhancing Perception and Action Feedback

The M2M2PA (Machine-to-Machine-to-Perception-and-Actuation) paradigm enhances traditional models by embedding:

- **Semantic Contextual Perception:** Context as structured, interpretable data;

Fig. 1. General architecture of an IoRT environment highlighting the role of the IoT Smart Hub. The Hub mediates communication between heterogeneous devices (sensors, actuators, voice assistants) and the cognitive multi-agent middleware via a semantic context manager, local contextual database, and Home Assistant + MQTT integration layer.

- **Action Validation and Feedback:** Execution verification for adaptive learning;
- **Cognitive Readiness:** Compatibility with LLMs and RL systems for high-level reasoning.

This turns the Hub into an active reasoning node, enabling robust interoperability and autonomous decision-making.

D. Cognitive Integration with LLMs

In IoRT, interpreting natural language and correlating it with environmental context is vital for adaptive behavior (18; 19). LLMs enable this interaction layer, acting as interpreters and planners. Rather than replacing core functions, they complement Smart Hub modules, especially under ambiguity (20).

1) Models Used: We evaluated:

- **Qwen 1.5-1.8B:** Local, open-source model optimized for edge execution, ensuring privacy and resilience;
- **GPT-4o (OpenAI API):** Frontier model with strong reasoning capabilities, used for comparative analysis.

This contrast allows evaluation between local robustness and cloud-level inference quality.

2) *Selection Criteria:* Qwen was chosen for its offline capabilities and license flexibility. Its use avoids privacy breaches and enables experiments with tuning and planning techniques. GPT-4o served as a baseline to measure reasoning depth and response efficiency (18).

A cost-benefit analysis guided use-case selection for either local or cloud-based execution.

E. ReAct Technique with Local Agent for Context Queries

We adopted the ReAct (Reasoning + Acting) method (18; 20) to enforce evidence-based decision-making. Agents interact with real tools (e.g., database queries) before formulating responses.

¹Frontier models include GPT-4o, Claude Opus 4, and Gemini 2.5 Pro.

Using LangChain, a ZERO_SHOT_REACT_DESCRIPTION agent was defined with strict behavioral rules:

- 1) Always query before responding;
- 2) Never fabricate data;
- 3) Conclude with a final, evidence-based answer.

Thought: Model’s internal reasoning.

Action: Tool to invoke.

Action Input: Query parameters.

Observation: Tool’s returned value.

Final Answer: Response to user.

F. SQLite Query Tools via LangChain

Agents interact with the environment through LangChain tools linked to SQLite. Defined tools include:

- `consultar_contexto_iot`: Retrieves latest sensor/actuator value/state;
- `simular_interacao_middleware`: Simulates user-environment interaction via middleware.

These tools enable structured and traceable queries, facilitating contextual understanding and future expansion.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

A. Simulations with Real Sensor Data

To validate the behavior of the proposed architecture in a controlled environment, a simulation was conducted using the `populate_db.py` script. This script systematically inserted a sequence of synthetic yet plausible sensor readings into the SQLite database, emulating real-time environmental dynamics such as changes in temperature, humidity, actuator states, and discrete events (e.g., doors or windows opening).

All data entries were recorded in the `contexto_ativo` table, structured as follows:

```
<id, timestamp, sensores, atuadores,
  eventos_iot, modo, submodo,
  interacao_middleware_id>
```

A representative JSON-formatted entry is shown below:

```
{
  "timestamp": "2025-05-22T11:14:09",
  "sensores": { "temperatura", "umidade" },
  "atuadores": { "atuador_estado": "ligado" },
  "eventos_iot": { "porta_ab":T, "janela_ab":F},
  "modo": "AUTOMATICO",
  "submodo": "PREFERENCIA"
}
```

This simulated environment enabled the LLM-based agent to retrieve and reason upon contextual information. When prompted with a question such as “Is the house comfortable?”, the ReAct agent would invoke the `consultar_contexto_iot()` tool to access the most recent contextual snapshot. The response was then synthesized based on multi-variable inference, including sensor data and actuator states.

This experiment successfully validated three critical functionalities:

- End-to-end flow: from sensor data ingestion to cognitive inference;

- Correct adoption of the ReAct schema during agent reasoning;
- Stable interaction between local perception, semantic storage, and LLM reasoning.

B. Use Cases: Status Query, Preferences, and Actions

A complete user-agent interaction exemplifying status inference is shown below:

User prompt: “Is it comfortable in the living room?”

Thought: Check current temperature and humidity data.

Action: `consultar_contexto_iot`

Action Input: “”

Observation: Temperature: 25.5°C, Humidity: 38.3%, Actuator: ON.

Thought: Environmental variables are within acceptable comfort thresholds.

Final Answer: Yes, the room is currently comfortable.

This demonstrates the system’s ability to perform contextual queries and return semantically coherent, data-driven responses aligned with user expectations.

C. Response Time and Agent Robustness

The performance of the two tested models, Qwen (local) and GPT-4o (API), was evaluated based on response latency and adherence to ReAct protocol during simulated tasks (21).

TABLE I
AVERAGE RESPONSE TIME AND REACT ROBUSTNESS

Model	Avg. Response Time	ReAct Robustness
Qwen 1.8B (local)	7.0 s	High (structured, consistent)
GPT-4o (via API)	2.3 s	High (natural, fluent)

The local Qwen model exhibited stable and repeatable behavior, correctly invoking tools and maintaining the prescribed format. Although GPT-4o offered lower latency and greater linguistic fluidity, its reliance on external connectivity may hinder its deployment in embedded or offline-first environments.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented the IoT Smart Hub, an edge-level, modular infrastructure designed to enhance adaptive interoperability and semantic contextualization in IoRT ecosystems. Grounded in the M2M2PA (Machine-to-Machine-to-Perception-and-Actuation) paradigm, the architecture connects low-level sensory layers with high-level reasoning by validating actions and structuring contextual feedback.

Preliminary experiments demonstrated that:

- Environmental data can be semantically organized and queried locally;
- Language models (LLMs) can reason over context-aware queries using the ReAct framework;
- The system supports both local (Qwen) and cloud-based (GPT-4o) cognitive agents with robust operation and low latency.

The integration of local models promotes offline operation and data privacy, while GPT-4o exemplifies the advantages of advanced reasoning in complex queries.

Nonetheless, current limitations include the absence of adaptive learning mechanisms, domain-specific fine-tuning of LLMs, and lack of dynamic ontological reasoning—factors targeted in the next research steps.

Future Work

Upcoming work includes: (i) building a CoppeliaSim-based testbed to validate planning and interoperability in IoRT; (ii) integrating lightweight ontologies for dynamic reasoning; (iii) enhancing cognition via reinforcement learning and multi-agent strategies; (iv) real-world deployment for assessing robustness; and (v) enabling fine-grained feedback to confirm physical execution of distributed sub-tasks in collaborative scenarios.

These developments aim to transform the IoT Smart Hub from a middleware layer into a truly intelligent node, capable of supporting autonomy, transparency, and long-term adaptation in increasingly complex IoRT systems.

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